

The Psalm Project 48

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 48

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 48:0 A Song; a Psalm of the sons of Korah.</p>	<p>Psa. 48:1 שִׁיר מְזֻמָּר לְבְנֵי-קָרַח : 2 וְדָוִד יִתְנַה וּמְהַלֵּל מְאֹד בְּעִיר אֱלֹהֵינוּ</p>
<p>Psa. 48:1 "Great is the LORD, and greatly to be praised,</p>	<p>הֶרְקָדְשׁוּ : 3 יִפְּחֵה נֹף מְשֹׁשׁ כָּל- הָאָרֶץ הֶרְ-צִיּוֹן יִרְכָּתִי צָפוֹן קָרְיַת</p>
<p>In the ^bcity of our God, His ^choly mountain.</p>	<p>מִלָּד רָב : 4 אֱלֹהִים בְּאַרְמְנוֹתֶיהָ נוֹרַע לְמִשְׁגָּב : 5 כִּי-הִנֵּה הַמַּלְכִים נוֹעְדוּ</p>
<p>² "Beautiful in elevation, ^bthe joy of the whole earth,</p>	<p>עָבְרוּ יַחְדָּו : 6 תִּמְחָה רָאוּ כֵן תִּמְחָהוּ נִבְהָלוּ נִחְפְּזוּ : 7 רַעְדָה אֲחֻזַּתֶם שָׁם</p>
<p>Is Mount Zion <i>in</i> the far north, The ^ccity of the great King.</p>	<p>חֵיִל כִּי-יִלְדָה : 8 בְּרוֹת קָדִים תִּשְׁבֵּר אֲנִיּוֹת תִּרְשִׁישׁ : 9 כַּאֲשֶׁר שָׁמַעְנוּ אֶפְן</p>
<p>³ God, in her palaces, Has made Himself known as a</p>	<p>רְאִינוּ בְּעִיר-יְהוָה צְבָאוֹת בְּעִיר אֱלֹהֵינוּ אֱלֹהִים יְכוֹנְנָה עַד-עוֹלָם</p>
<p>"stronghold.</p>	<p>סָלָה : 10 דְּמִינוּ אֱלֹהִים חֲסֻדָּךְ בְּקִרְבִּי הִיכָלְךָ : 11 כְּשִׁמְךָ אֱלֹהִים כֵּן תִּהְלֶתְךָ</p>
<p>Psa. 48:4 For, lo, the ^akings assembled themselves,</p>	<p>עַל-קְצוֹי-אָרֶץ צָדַק מְלֵאָה יְמִינְךָ : 12 יִשְׂמַח אֶת-רֶ-צִיּוֹן תִּגְלָנָה בְּנוֹת יְהוּדָה</p>
<p>They passed by together.</p>	<p>לְמַעַן מִשְׁפָּטֶיךָ : 13 סָבוּ צִיּוֹן וְהִקִּיפוּהָ סָפְרוּ מִגְדָּלֶיהָ : 14 שִׁיתוּ לְבָבָם </p>
<p>⁵ They saw <i>it</i>, then they were amazed;</p>	<p>לְחִילָה פָּסְגוּ אַרְמְנוֹתֶיהָ לְמַעַן תִּסְפְּרוּ לְדֹר אַחֲרָיוֹן : 15 כִּי זֶה אֱלֹהִים אֱלֹהֵינוּ עוֹלָם וָעַד הוּא יִנְהַגְנוּ עַל-</p>
<p>They were ^aterrified, they ¹fled in alarm.</p>	<p>מוֹת :</p>
<p>⁶ ¹Panic seized them there, Anguish, as of ^a"a woman in childbirth.</p>	
<p>⁷ With the ^aeast wind You ^bbreak the ^cships of Tarshish.</p>	
<p>⁸ As we have heard, so have we seen</p>	
<p>In the city of the LORD of hosts, in the city of our God;</p>	
<p>God will ^aestablish her forever. ¹Selah.</p>	
<p>Psa. 48:9 We have thought on ^aYour lovingkindness, O God,</p>	
<p>In the midst of Your temple.</p>	

<p>¹⁰ As is Your ^aname, O God, So is Your ^bpraise to the ends of the earth; Your ^cright hand is full of righteousness.</p> <p>¹¹ Let Mount ^aZion be glad, Let the ^adaughters of Judah rejoice Because of Your judgments.</p> <p>¹² Walk about Zion and go around her; Count her ^atowers;</p> <p>¹³ Consider her ^aramparts; Go through her palaces, That you may ^btell <i>it</i> to the next generation.</p> <p>¹⁴ For ¹such is God, Our God forever and ever; He will ^aguide us ²until death.</p>	
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References

<p>Psalm 48:1 ^a1 Chr 16:25; Ps 96:4; 145:3 ^bPs 46:4 ^cPs 2:6; 87:1; Is 2:3; Mic 4:1; Zech 8:3</p> <p>Psalm 48:2 ^aPs 50:2 ^bLam 2:15 ^cMatt 5:35</p> <p>Psalm 48:3 ^aPs 46:7</p> <p>Psalm 48:4 ^a2 Sam 10:6-19</p> <p>Psalm 48:5 ¹Lit <i>were hurried away</i> ^aEx 15:15</p> <p>Psalm 48:6 ¹Lit <i>Trembling</i> ^aIs 13:8</p> <p>Psalm 48:7 ^aJer 18:17 ^b1 Kin 22:48 ^c1 Kin 10:22; Ezek 27:25</p> <p>Psalm 48:8 ¹<i>Selah</i> may mean: <i>Pause, Crescendo</i> or <i>Musical interlude</i> ^aPs 87:5</p> <p>Psalm 48:9 ^aPs 26:3; 40:10</p>	<p>Psalm 48:10 ^aDeut 28:58; Josh 7:9; Mal 1:11 ^bPs 65:1, 2; 100:1 ^cIs 41:10</p> <p>Psalm 48:11 ^aPs 97:8</p> <p>Psalm 48:12 ^aNeh 3:1, 11, 25-27</p> <p>Psalm 48:13 ^aPs 122:7 ^bPs 78:5-7</p> <p>Psalm 48:14 ¹Lit <i>this</i> ²Lit <i>upon</i>; some mss and the Gr read <i>forever</i> ^aPs 23:4; Is 58:11</p>
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Targum

Psa. 48:1 A song and psalm by the sons of Korah. ² Great is the LORD and very praiseworthy, in Jerusalem, the city of our God, and on the mount of his sanctuary. ³ Beautiful as a bridegroom, the joy of all the inhabitants of the earth, Mount Zion, on the north side, the city of the great king. ⁴ The LORD is in its palaces; it is known for strength. ⁵ For behold, the kings have joined forces, they have passed by together. ⁶ They have seen, so they were amazed at the miracles and wonders; they were astonished, yea, they fled. ⁷ Trembling seized them there, agitation like a woman giving birth. ⁸ With an east wind strong as fire from the presence of the LORD, you will shatter the ships of Tarsis. ⁹ The children of Israel will say, “Just as we have heard, so we have seen; in the city of the LORD Sabaoth, in the city of our God – the LORD will establish it forever and ever.” ¹⁰ Make us worthy, O LORD, of your goodness in the midst of your temple. ¹¹ As your name, O LORD, so is your praise to the ends of the earth; your right hand is full of generosity. ¹² Let Mount Zion rejoice, let the assemblies of the house of Judah rejoice with psalms, because of your judgments. ¹³ Surround Zion, let them rejoice, and encircle her, number her towers. ¹⁴ Set your mind on her throngs above, [even on] her citadels, that you may tell it to another generation. ¹⁵ For this, the LORD, he is our God; his presence is in her midst and his dwelling is in heaven forever and ever; he will guide us in the days of our youth.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

The Psalmist describes the future glory of Jerusalem. The rebuilding of the city signals an era of national renewal.

Superscript

A song, a psalm by the sons of Korach

Verse one

“Great is the LORD” is an interesting statement. It indicates that the LORD surpasses every concept humans might have to the power and divine force that rules and shapes the world. What humans cannot do, the LORD can.

Great is the LORD and clearly revealed by His mighty acts in Jerusalem on Mount Zion, His holy mountain.

Verse two

The north of Jerusalem is where the Temple and palaces were located in ancient days.

Beautiful in its view, a joy to all the world. Mount Zion’s northern summit, the city of the great King (the LORD).

Verse three

The LORD's greatness is found in other places than just the Temple. The city of Jerusalem with its palaces is one example.

In its palaces, God has been recognized as a stronghold.

Verses four, five, six, and seven

These verses refer to the kings that came together to attack Israel. They grabbed a lot of the land of the Promised land, but they could not take Jerusalem. This sounds like the events when the Assyrians invaded. They were able to seize the land of Judea, but when they got to Jerusalem, the LORD defeated them.

For, lo, the kings assembled themselves, they passed by together.

They saw *it*, then they were amazed; they were terrified, they fled in alarm.

Panic seized them there, anguish, as of a woman in childbirth.

With the east wind, You break the ships of Tarshish.

Verse eight

The greatness of the LORD was told from generation to generation. The psalmist expresses his love for the LORD because he (or they) have experienced the LORD's love for themselves.

Even as we have heard it in the past, so have we seen it now in Jerusalem, the city of the LORD, who established it forever. Meditate on this verse.

Verses nine, ten, and eleven

The name of the LORD brings praises to the wonders and beauty of His creation.

We have thought on Your lovingkindness, O God, in the midst of Your temple.

As is Your name, O God, so is Your praise to the ends of the earth; Your right hand is full of righteousness.

Let Mount Zion be glad, let the daughters of Judah rejoice because of Your judgments.

Verses twelve and thirteen

Israel is called to preserve the city of Jerusalem. They are also charged with proclaiming prosperity that the nation's spiritual, moral, and political soul dwells amid Mount Zion and Jerusalem. This city is the center of Israel.

Rally around Mount Zion, gather around her closely, count her towers,

Set your heart on the circular wall, raise her palaces aloft so that you may tell of it to all future generations.

Verse fourteen

The LORD will lead Israel beyond mortality.

This God is our God forever. He leads us beyond mortality.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A song, a psalm by the sons of Korach

Great is the LORD and clearly revealed by His mighty acts in Jerusalem on Mount Zion, His holy mountain.

Beautiful in its view, a joy to all the world. Mount Zion's northern summit, the city of the great King (the LORD).

In its palaces, God has been recognized as a stronghold.

For, lo, the kings assembled themselves, they passed by together.

They saw *it*, then they were amazed; they were terrified, they fled in alarm. Panic seized them there, anguish, as of a woman in childbirth.

With the east wind, You break the ships of Tarshish.

Even as we have heard it in the past, so have we seen it now in Jerusalem, the city of the LORD, who established it forever. Meditate on this verse.

We have thought on Your lovingkindness, O God, in the midst of Your temple.

As is Your name, O God, so is Your praise to the ends of the earth; Your right hand is full of righteousness.

Let Mount Zion be glad, let the daughters of Judah rejoice because of Your judgments.

Rally around Mount Zion, gather around her closely, count her towers,

Set your heart on the circular wall, raise her palaces aloft so that you may tell of it to all future generations.

This God is our God forever. He leads us beyond mortality.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

